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SALTOpower

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D1.6: Gender Equality Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

D1.6 is a report on the implementation and impacts of the Gender Equality (GE) activities in SALTOpower, pertaining to Task 1.4, which aimed at the development and implementation of questionnaires, 4 dedicated seminars, monitoring procedures and enhancement strategies for Gender Equality in the access to research and technical-administrative positions in the Consortium institutions, concurring with the attractiveness of Young Researchers to UÉvora (SALTOpower Objective 3).

Led by UÉvora, Task 1.4 acknowledges the importance of promoting and monitoring Gender Equality aspects both in the Widening upgrade and in having a gender balanced perspective in research and technical-administrative teams. The activities are based on the UÉvora Gender Equality Plan - GEP (first version in 2022-2023, second version for 2024-2026, including an English translation), which focuses on the following aspects, according to the Horizon Europe recommendations:

- work-life balance and organisational culture;
- gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content;
- measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

Horizon Europe prioritises gender equality, aiming to integrate it into research and innovation content and ensure gender-equal working environments, aiming to eliminate gender and intersecting inequalities.

Several statistics show that there is still work to be done to achieve this goal, for instance, women accounted for 24% of employees in the EU energy sector in 2022, and in renewable energy, women represented 32% of full-time employees globally in 2018².

At the EU level, considering all fields, gender balance is achieved among university students and graduates, but as women advance in academia, their representation decreases, especially at top positions, holding only 30% of full professorship (or equivalent) positions. In Science and Engineering, this percentage drops to 20%. Women remain underrepresented as authors in the field of Engineering and Technology, and women comprised only 9% of patent applicants in the 2018-2021 period³.

However, gender diversity is not only fair but also represents an advantage for research and innovation. First, for not leaving a huge potential of talent unexplored. Then, because several studies found that a high proportion of women in scientific teams contributes to successful team collaboration (possibly, because women show greater social sensitivity, being more likely to collaborate and being more democratic), catalysing creativity and innovation, increasing collective intelligence and best outcomes. Nevertheless, there isn't an ideal proportion of women on a team established, also because it is not only a question of *"the number of women, but rather how women on teams are integrated and empowered"*⁴.

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

² Webinar "Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition", European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), in the 14th of November of 2023

³ "She Figures 2024 - Research and Innovation", <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/she-figures-2024>

⁴ Love, H.B., Stephens, A., Fosdick, B.K., *et al.* The impact of gender diversity on scientific research teams: a need to broaden and accelerate future research. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 9, 386 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01389-w>

To monitor the gender balance, a comparison of the 3 partners' GEPs (UÉvora, DLR and ENEA) was held, as well as an analysis of the number of employees by gender.

The UÉvora team attended dedicated GE events and organised an internal leadership training.

Four dedicated seminars have already been held, alongside project meetings, and a fifth one is foreseen for the final meeting in October 2025. These seminars addressed different topics and promoted debates.

A survey was conducted using a questionnaire applied to all the consortium SALTOpower teams and to the Fast-Track Schools (FTS) participants.

This topic was also covered in the project's communication channels, and the mentioned activities are detailed below.

2. SALTOPOWER GENDER BALANCE

Gender analysis provides information on the different roles of women and men at different levels in institutions and projects, enabling an understanding of gender inequalities. When focused on institutions, gender analysis is also important in determining how institutions themselves are also 'gendered', for example, in the workplace in terms of recruitment practices, the gendered divisions of labour and women's access to decision-making positions⁵.

Therefore, the data provided by UÉvora, ENEA and DLR were compared, taking into account the employees of these institutions in general, and the SALTOpower team members, in specific (both by M17 and M34). The gender proportion of the FTS participants was also analysed.

2.1 Consortium Institutions

2.1.1 UÉvora

Troughout 2021, in UÉvora, a gender diagnosis was held entitled "Perceções e Realidades sobre a (In)Visibilidade de Género na Universidade de Évora. Relatório de diagnóstico institucional"⁶ (Perceptions and Realities on Gender (In)Visibility at the University of Évora. Institutional diagnostic report). The document was published in January 2022. Contributions were collected from employees at all hierarchical levels and functional areas, ensuring a plural and representative view. In the same year, the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) was published, based on the results of the diagnosis.

In this diagnosis, it was verified that from the 1121 employees (in 2021), 54.77% were women and 45.23% were men. In the professors and researchers category, 47.17% were women and 52.84% men, and in the non-teaching staff (including scholarship holders), 62% were women and 38% were men.

Regarding the top positions, the percentages were: leading researchers - 33.3% women, 66.7% men; full professors - 33.3% women, 66.7% men; non-teaching managers - 64.9% women, 35.1% men.

By 2022, the Renewable Energies Chair - CER (where the SALTOpower team is included), from UÉvora, presented the most significant male overrepresentation, with 80.55% of men and 19.45% of women among the researchers and scholarship holders. Nowadays (January 2025), this percentage has changed, along with the growth of the group to 72% of men and 28% of women.

⁵ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/tools-methods/gender-analysis>

⁶ <https://dspace.uevora.pt/rdpc/handle/10174/33273>

A new diagnostic report in UÉvora is foreseen for 2026.

2.1.2 ENEA

In ENEA, in 2021, there were 2311 employees, of whom 58.98% were men and 41.02% women. Table 2.1.2.1 presents these percentages by position category.

Table 2.1.2.1: Percentage of women and men, by category, in ENEA (2021)

Position Category	Men (%)	Women (%)
Researcher	61.65	38.35
Technologist	49.02	50.98
Administrative	32.35	67.65
Technician	64.56	35.44
Overall	58.98	41.02

As ENEA has regularly updated information on gender balance, the latest data available are from 2024 (with a total of 2215 employees, 57.17% were men and 42.83% women), and are presented in Table 2.1.2.2.

Table 2.1.2.2: Percentage of women and men, by category, in ENEA (2024)

Position Category	Men (%)	Women (%)
Researcher	60.21	39.79
Technologist	46.25	53.75
Administrative	30.73	69.27
Technician	65.12	34.88
Overall	57.17	42.83

2.1.3 DLR

DLR also has regular diagnosis, and gender balance is taken into account on the assumption that “excellent research needs all talents”, and measures are being taken to address the persistent under-representation of women in STEM professions. Target quotas for women in science are regularly set to achieve a more balanced participation of female scientists at all levels, especially in management positions.

In 2021, of 10326 employees, 34.30% were women and 65.70% men. Regarding scientific staff, 22.69% were women and 77.31% men; and among the top positions, 20.90% were women and 79.10% men.

In 2024, of 11787 employees, 34.27% were women and 65.73% men. Regarding scientific staff, 20.78% were women and 79.22% men; and among the top positions, 21.66% were women and 78.34% men.

2.1.4 Comparison

For all three institutions, it was possible to access data from 2021, and more recent data from 2024 for ENEA and DLR (as there are annual data available).

It was verified that, at UÉvora, the Human Resources database does not include gender data for all employees, which makes it difficult to check the number of women and men in the

institution regularly. This is one of the measures that the Widening partner could develop, following the example of the TOP partners of SALTOpower.

To enable the comparison between the partners' institutions, in Table 2.1.4.1 and Figure 2.1.4.1, employees are presented by gender (women and men) and by general category: "researchers" (including researchers, professors, leadership positions and technologists) and "other staff" (including scholarship holders, administrative staff and technicians).

Table 2.1.4.1: Percentage of women and men, by category, in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR (2021)

Partner	Researchers - Men (%)	Researchers - Women (%)	Other staff - Men (%)	Other staff - Women (%)	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora	52.84	47.17	38.02	61.98	45.23	54.77
ENEA	59.42	40.58	58.25	41.75	58.98	41.02
DLR	77.31	22.69	45.13	54.87	65.70	34.30

Figure 2.1.4.1: Proportion of women and men, by category, in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR (2021)

2.2 SALTOpower teams

The number of women and men in the three SALTOpower partners' teams was monitored both when submitting D1.4 - Progress Report, in M17 (March 2024), and in M34 (August 2025) for this D1.6, to make an assessment of the gender balance in the project and its evolution, as new members joined the team. Overall, there was an improvement in the gender balance (in agreement with the recommendation of incorporating more female researchers in the general project review consolidated report), although there are still more men researchers and more women in "other staff".

The WP leaders' positions in the three partners teams are now occupied by men.

Fewer women and for less time went on mobility, and a significantly lower number of CYR (PhD students) are women.

The number of YR, for the all project, presents no difference in the number of researchers by gender. The mentoring program showed no significant gender unbalance, with a low number of registrations.

Figure 2.2.1: SALTOpower team in the Kick-off meeting (November 22) and in ProM#6 (May 25)

2.2.1 M17 teams

In M17 (March 2024), the SALTOpower teams (researchers and other workforce involved in the project's Action) were distributed by gender as follows in Table 2.2.1.1 and Figure 2.2.2.2.1.

Table 2.2.1.1: Gender distribution in the SALTOpower team in M17

Partner	Researchers - Men	Researchers - Women	Other staff - Men	Other staff - Women	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora	4	1	0	4	44.44	55.56
ENEA	4	5	1	0	50.00	50.00
DLR	4	1	0	1	66.67	33.33
Total	12	7	1	5	52.00	48.00

2.2.2 M34 teams

In M34 (August 2025), the SALTOpower teams (researchers and other workforce involved in the project's Action) were distributed by gender as follows in Table 2.2.2.1 and Figure 2.2.2.2.1.

Table 2.2.2.1: Gender distribution in the SALTOpower team in M34

Partner	Researchers - Men	Researchers - Women	Other staff - Men	Other staff - Women	Total - Men (%)	Total - Women (%)
UÉvora	5	3	0	3	45.45	54.55
ENEA	8	7	1	1	52.94	47.06
DLR	3	3	0	0	50.00	50.00
Total	16	13	1	4	50.00	50.00

Figure 2.2.2.1: Proportion of women and men, by category, in SALTOpower, in M17 and in M34

2.2.3 Gender balance in SALTOpower top positions

The PSC - Project Steering Committee, including all the WP leaders (one per partner), until M17 was composed of 2 men and 1 woman, after which, with a change in the DLR team leader, the PSC is now composed of 3 men.

2.2.4 Gender balance in SALTOpower activities

The SALTOpower teams took part in activities in the scope of the project (see D3.3 Career attractiveness framework report), including a leadership training (only the UÉvora team), mobilities (travels in the scope of project coordination, tutoring and mentoring tasks), PhD thesis tutoring (CYR - Task 3.2), mentoring of YR (Task 3.3), and a mentoring program (in the scope of the Living Amenities Facility, task 3.4), in which the gender balance is presented in this section.

In the leadership training, besides being in itself a GE action (see section 4.1), the gender of the participants can also be assessed: a female coach led the training in May 2025, for 11 participants: 4 women and 7 men, from the UÉvora CER group. A percentage of 36.36% of women participants in the leadership training (1 more woman researcher wanted to participate, but couldn't due to a health problem, which would change the percentage to 41.67%), compared to 28% of women researchers in the CER group, shows that the women in the group want to progress in their careers and feel supported by the team.

Researchers and other staff mobility were held, with the team members of UÉvora, DLR and ENEA travelling between the partners' institutions' locations to take part in Coordination activities (project meetings, GE seminars, Spin-off seminars, visits to research infrastructures, FTSS, tutoring and mentoring tasks, etc.). Table 2.2.4.1 summarises the number of mobilities by partner and by gender, including UÉvora researchers' mobilities to TOP partners already booked for M35. Until the end of the project, some more mobilities are foreseen, but still not booked, namely for the final meeting and from TOP partners YR and CYR researchers to the Widening partner.

Table 2.2.4.1: Gender distribution in the SALTOpower mobilities, researchers and other staff, by M35

Partner	Men (% of mobilities in number of days)	Women (% of mobilities in number of days)	Men (% of persons travelling)	Women (% of persons travelling)
UÉvora	58.58	41.42	50.00	50.00
ENEA	68.75	31.25	55.56	44.44
DLR	50.00	50.00	63.64	36.36
Total	58.81	41.19	56.67	43.33

Figure 2.2.4.1: UÉvora researchers (YR and CYR) in a mobility to DLR and SALTOpower teams in a visit to UÉvora research infrastructure

With regard to the PhD tutoring activities (Task 3.2, WP3), the Candidate Young Researchers (CYR), by partner and by gender, are presented in Table 2.2.4.2.

Table 2.2.4.2: Gender distribution in the SALTOpower CYR

Partner	Men (% of CYR)	Women (% of CYR)
UÉvora	100.00	0.00
ENEA	100.00	0.00
DLR	50.00	50.00
Total	83.33	16.67

Regarding the mentoring of Young Researchers (YR) activities (Task 3.3, WP3), the YR, by partner and by gender, are presented in Table 2.2.4.3.

Table 2.2.4.3: Gender distribution in the SALTOpower YR

Partner	Men (% of YR)	Women (% of YR)
UÉvora	25.00	75.00
ENEA	75.00	25.00
DLR	0.00	0.00
Total	50.00	50.00

The mentoring program in the scope of the Living Amenities Facility (Task 3.4, WP3), with five registrations, includes 2 female mentors and 3 mentorees, 1 woman and 2 men, thus 40% of men and 60% of women.

2.3 SALTOpower events

2.3.1 Fast-Track Schools

There were three editions of the SALTOpower FTs (see D3.1), but the gender only began to be collected in the second edition.

For FTS#2, there were 76 registrations, being 22 women (28.95%) and 54 men (71.10%) (Figure 2.3.1.1). From the registered participants, 51 attended (onsite or online), being 18 women (35.29%) and 33 men (64.71%).

Figure 2.3.1.1: Gender of the registered participants of FTS#2

For FTS#3, there were 56 answers regarding gender in the registrations, being 17 women (30.40%), 38 men (67.90%), a one person preferred not to say the gender (1.8%) (Figure 2.3.1.3). From the registered participants, 44 attended (onsite - Figure 2.3.1.4 or online), being 16 women (36.36%) and 28 men (63.64%).

Figure 2.3.1.3: Gender of the registered participants of FTS#3

Figure 2.3.1.4: FTS#3 onsite participants

2.3.2 Other events

SALTOpower also organised Fora and Simposia (see D4.1), but the gender was not collected in the registrations, in some cases because the registration was by email, not using a form, in other cases, like in small group debates, because the participants were directly invited.

As gender identity refers to “socially constructed attributes, roles, activities, responsibilities and needs”⁷, one's own gender is to be identified by each person, so it can not be deduced by others. With this concept defined, the following statements are limited to observation and contact with participants, as their gender was not questioned to them.

In the SALTOpower Energy Strategy Symposium (ESSymp), a national symposium organised in Évora, the gender balance appears to be even (Figure 2.3.2.1). However, when looking at the participants who presented their companies (top positions in energy companies) and took part in a round-table, they are all men.

Figure 2.3.2.1: ESSymp participants

In the SALTOpower Energy Transition Symposium (ETSymp), an international symposium organised online, in the first phase, there was a debate with a small group in each partner country, where the participants appeared to be mostly men (Figure 2.3.2.3).

Figure 2.3.2.3: ETSymp national day: Portugal

In the ETSymp second phase, an international online day was held, and the gender balance appeared to be even (Figure 2.3.2.4). Following this event, a satisfaction survey was sent to the participants, and of the 26 external participants, 14 answered it, including a question about their gender (Figure 2.3.2.5). Although this sample may not reflect the gender of all the participants, it was answered by 10 men (71.40%) and 4 women (28.60%).

7

https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/gender_en

Figure 2.3.2.4: ETSymp international day

5. Gender:
14 respostas

Figure 2.3.2.5: Gender of the participants answering the ETSymp international day survey

3. GEP COMPARISON

The three partner institutions of the SALTOpower consortium have published Gender Equality Plans (GEPs, Figure 3.1) and their analysis, together with that of complementary documents⁸, has provided insight into the approaches of UÉvora, ENEA and DLR to GE issues and institutional diagnostics.

⁸

<https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Gender%20Equality/Gender%20Equality%20Plans>

Figure 3.1: UÉvora, DLR, and ENEA’s Gender Equality Plans

The first UÉvora GEP was published in January 2022, with the 2022-2023 strategy, and a similar second version for 2024-2026 was published, including an English translation.

After analysing the three GEPs, it can be concluded that all the Plans follow the European and national legislations, as well as the Horizon Europe guidance on GEPs, focusing on the points:

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

All the institutions have made a situation diagnosis to learn about the gender balance of their employees, with different frequencies, and UÉvora also applied a questionnaire and conducted focus groups to understand the existing perceptions around the previous 5 points. All plans set objectives to be achieved and tools/measures to implement, and agree that continuous monitoring is necessary.

The differences found in the GEPs are mostly in the measures proposed and/or implemented by each institution, as presented in Tables 3.1.1 to 3.1.5.

Table 3.1.1: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR GEPs, point 1

Partner	Work-life balance and organisational culture
All	Flexibility of schedules Use of non-sexist language Teleworking Summer campus/holiday activities for children
UÉvora	Drafting of a practical guide in inclusive language Awareness campaigns Childcare services Meetings with a maximum of 2 hours long
ENEA	Teleworking for workers with specific family situations Economical support during parental leave Day care centres for elderly cohabiting parents Meetings within working hours
DLR	Reserved places in childcare centres

	<p>Online seminars and informative materials (intranet, flyers...)</p> <p>Promoting the assumption of family responsibilities by men</p> <p>Family advisory centre (family care, coming back after parental leave...)</p> <p>Online workshops for children</p> <p>Part-time work during parental leave</p>
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Table 3.1.2: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR GEPs, point 2

Partner	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making
All	<p>Monitoring the composition of the leadership bodies</p> <p>Training with experts and mentoring</p>

Table 3.1.3: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR GEPs, point 3

Partner	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
UÉvora	Equality in selection boards
ENEA	<p>Neutral job advertisements</p> <p>Sensitising managers to GE and selection procedures (e.g. it is unacceptable to ask about marital status, pregnancy or family responsibilities in interviews)</p>
DLR	<p>Equality in selection boards</p> <p>Positive discrimination in hiring</p> <p>Female candidates encouraged</p> <p>Celebration of Girls' National Day and visits by girls from regional schools</p> <p>Neutral job advertisements</p> <p>Sensitising managers to GE and selection procedures (e.g. it is unacceptable to ask about marital status, pregnancy or family responsibilities in interviews)</p>

Table 3.1.4: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR GEPs, point 4

Partner	Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content
UÉvora	<p>To include GE in more study programmes</p> <p>Training and raising awareness</p>
ENEA	<p>Promotional videos about female researchers and technicians' R&D activities</p> <p>Health promotion for women workers, gender-related workplace risk assessment</p>
DLR	<p>Target quotas for scientific staff</p> <p>Accelerated recruitment processes</p> <p>Increasing women's visibility</p>

Table 3.1.5: Proposed/implemented measures in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR GEPs, point 5

Partner	Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment
All	<p>Training</p> <p>In case of complaints: how, to whom, how to manage, conduct code</p>
UÉvora	<p>Scientific and artistic events</p> <p>In case of complaints: by e-mail (whistleblowing channel on the institutional website)</p>
ENEA	<p>Seminars and campaigns</p> <p>Confidential counselling helpline</p> <p>In case of complaints: by e-mail, internet materials</p>

DLR	Confidential counselling helpline Confidentially appointed persons with specific training to share information In case of complaints: intranet guide
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Overall, the three GEPs identify that in UÉvora, ENEA and DLR, there is a predominantly non-sexist culture, nevertheless, certain positions or functions are occupied by men, and inclusive language must be used.

The UÉvora diagnosis, using focus groups and questionnaires, verified that women are more interested in debating/approaching GE themes, and that there are numerous questions and doubts about how, to whom or whether it is worth reporting gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

4. GE ACTIONS IN THE CONSORTIUM AND GE EVENTS ATTENDED BY THE SALTOPower TEAM

To promote GE among SALTOpower partners, relevant documents, campaigns, training courses and other events in which the teams could participate were identified, with particular emphasis on the Widening partner, which could learn from examples applied by TOP partners (see 4.1).

To increase their knowledge and bring more content to the SALTOpower GE seminars, the technical-administrative members of the UÉvora team participate in events related to GE (see 4.2) and maintain a close collaboration with the University of Évora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion (Gabinete de Igualdade de Género e Inclusão da Universidade de Évora). This Office was established in 2019, but currently has only one employee assigned to it, who often collaborates in the SALTOpower GE seminars.

4.1 GE Actions in the Consortium

Following a SALTOpower GE seminar where gender-sensitive communication was referred to, ENEA shared its guide “Linee guida per il linguaggio di genere in ENEA” (Guidelines for gender-neutral language at ENEA)⁹.

ENEA also shared the promotional video¹⁰ “For Women in Science” (Figure 4.1.1).

Both the guide and the video were shared with the UÉvora Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion.

Figure 4.1.1: ENEA “For Women in Science” promotional video

⁹ Available in <https://www.cug.enea.it/attivita-del-cug/generi-e-linguaggi.html> and https://teamsites-extranet.dlr.de/sites/EUSALTOPower/Documents/Management/Gender%20Equality/Gender%20Equality%20Seminar_october23/2022%2004%2028%20LINEE%20GUIDA.PDF

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=P7SORDotGmc>

("ENEA dedicates this video to all women who work to understand the world and try to improve it")

In 2023 and 2025, in the scope of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, UÉvora published testimonials from its female scientists¹¹, in the first year with texts published on the UÉvora website and, this year, with a promotional video available in several communication channels, including UÉvora social networks (Figure 4.1.2).

Figure 4.1.2: UÉvora "Women in Science" promotional video

UÉvora SALTOpower technical-administrative team recommended to all the project team members:

- the "Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication" from the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) and suggested to take the quizzes on inclusive language available on the EIGE website¹²;
- the NAU website 3-hour training course on "Gender Equality in Labour and Employment", run by the Instituto do Emprego e Formação Profissional, I.P. (IEFP - Institute for Employment and Vocational Training) and the Comissão para a Igualdade no Trabalho e no Emprego (CITE - Commission for Equality in Labour and Employment), only available in Portuguese¹³.

A leadership training also took place with the UÉvora team, including SALTOpower's researchers, in May 2025 (Figure 4.1.3), as referred to in D3.3 (section 3.2).

Figure 4.1.3: SALTOpower team in the leadership training in Évora

By the end of the training, a satisfaction survey was applied and received 11 answers, and as it was not included in D3.3, which was submitted before the training, some of the questions and respective answers are presented in Table 4.1.1.

¹¹ <https://www.uevora.pt/ue-media/Mulheres-na-Ciencia>

¹²

<https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/toolkits-guides/gender-sensitive-communication/common-challenges-when-using-gender-sensitive-language>

¹³ <https://www.nau.edu.pt/en/course/igualdade-de-genero-no-trabalho-e-no-emprego/>

Table 4.1.1: Answers to the leadership training satisfaction survey

Question	Classification
Do you believe the knowledge gained is applicable to your professional context?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Not at all ● Slightly ● Applicable ● Very applicable
Did the training contribute to your development as a leader/researcher?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly disagree ● Disagree ● Agree ● Strongly agree
What is your overall level of satisfaction with the training?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Very dissatisfied ● Dissatisfied ● Satisfied ● Very satisfied
After this training, I will...	

4.2 GE Events attended

To improve their knowledge and bring more content to the SALTOpower GE seminars, the technical-administrative members of the UÉvora team participate in events related to GE, online or organised by the University (Figure 4.2.1). Table 4.2.1 lists these events.

Figure 4.2.1: The conference "The verb To Be in the feminine" as the cover of the UÉvora magazine "À Segunda" (cover headline: "UÉvora discusses the role of women in society")

Table 4.2.1: GE-related events attended by UÉvora SALTOpower team members

Date	Event	Location/Organisation
April 2023	2nd Iberian conferences "The verb To Be in the feminine - Inclusion, Equality, and Health at work"	UÉvora
September 2023	Themed visit to the Évora Museum: "Where are the women?"	UÉvora and Évora's Frei Manuel do Cenáculo National Museum
November 2023	Woman Impact Summit	Online, Heroikka
February 2024	Webinar "Leadership in feminine"	Online, AMONET, the Portuguese Association of Women Scientists
June 2024	Civil Security for Everyone - Sex and Gender in Research on Civil Security	Online, European Research Area Workshops on the Gender Dimension in Research
September 2024	Webinar "Equality between women and men"	Online, State Legal Competence Centre, CIG - Commission for Citizenship and Gender Equality
November 2024	Webinar "Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition"	Online, EIGE
February 2025	Gender dimension in your Horizon Europe proposal	Online, Europa Media Trainings Webinar
May 2025	2nd edition of the Gender, Diversity, Citizenship colloquium	UÉvora
May 2025	"Science, Gender Equality and Women Scientists: Building Inclusive Research Environments"	Online, Ibero-American Program for Education in Human Rights, Democracy and Equality of the OEI and EU-Solaris ERIC

5. SALTOPower GE SEMINARS

Task 1.4 includes the organisation of four dedicated seminars, alongside the Project Meetings (ProM) and hosted, in turns, by the Widening and the TOP partners, in M7 (ENEA), M13 (UÉvora), M19 (DLR), and M36 (UÉvora), which was accomplished, with a few adjustments.

Four seminars have already been held, with a second online seminar complementing the first one, and a fifth seminar will be organised along with the Project Final Meeting (#7). UÉvora technical-administrative SALTOpower team organised and presented the seminars, with the collaboration of the UÉvora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion manager, and the participation of all partners teams.

The first seminar was held in M7, in Rome (see 5.1 ProM#2 GE Seminar), the second seminar in M12 as a complementary extra online seminar (see 5.2 Online GE Seminar), the third seminar in M13, in Évora (see 5.3 ProM#3 GE Seminar), and the fourth seminar in M21, instead of M19, to be along with ProM in Cologne (see 5.4 ProM#4 GE Seminar), and the fifth seminar will be organised, as foreseen, in M36, in Évora (see 5.5 ProM#7 GE Seminar).

After the presentations, the seminars included guided discussions regarding the actions to be taken in SALTOpower and GE perceptions. In some of the seminars, there was greater interest among women in actively participating in the discussion.

One of the main conclusions of the debates was that parenting, especially for new parents, particularly mothers, is where there are greater difficulties in balancing personal/family life and professional life and more negative consequences for the careers of female researchers.

5.1 ProM#2 GE Seminar

The first SALTOPower GE seminar, presented by UÉvora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion manager (Célia Peralta), focused on the UÉvora GEP, when and how it was developed, and its contents (Appendix 2). A summary of this seminar is presented in Table 5.1.1.

Table 5.1.1: ProM#2 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#2 GE Seminar
Date	9 May 2023
Project Month	M7
Location/Host	ENEA Casaccia Research Centre, Rome / ENEA
Presentation	Célia Peralta (UÉvora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion)
Participants	UÉvora, ENEA and DLR SALTOpower teams participating in ProM#2
Number of participants per gender	6 men, 7 women
Duration	30 minutes
Main topic	UÉvora GEP

As the seminar focused mainly on UÉvora GEP, it was decided to organise an extra seminar, online, as a complement, to gather more input from partners on how and which GE measures to apply in SALTOpower and the Widening institution.

Figure 5.1.1: ProM#2 GE Seminar participants (among other SALTOpower event attendees, with Célia Peralta on the left), and a presentation slide of the GE seminar

5.2 Online GE Seminar

The online GE seminar, in October 2023, was organised by UÉvora, and all partners teams were invited, by email, to attend online. A summary of this seminar is presented in Table 5.2.1, and it focused on why to include gender dimension topics in the project, some concepts related to the theme were clarified (the glass ceiling effect, the cement ceiling effect, and the Matilda effect), a comparison between UÉvora, DLR and ENEA GE Plans and applied or suggested measures in these plans (see section 3), main achievements - mandatory GEPs, more often discussions on the GE topics, legislation, more women in leadership positions, more flexible parental leave policies, more inclusive working environments - and main problems in GE - how to report gender-based discrimination or violence, there are still less women in STEM, lack of consequences to the offenders - the publication of the “Code of conduct for the prevention and combat of harassment at work in UÉvora” in June 2023, how to do a GE assessment in SALTOpower, with the presentation of T1.4 in the project proposal, and examples of measures to be taken (Appendix 2).

Table 5.2.1: Online GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	Online GE Seminar
Date	16 October 2023
Project Month	M7
Location/Host	Online / UÉvora
Presentation	Célia Peralta (UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion) Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s SALTOPower technical-administrative support)
Participants	UÉvora, and ENEA SALTOpower teams
Number of participants per gender	2 men, 5 women
Duration	60 minutes
Main topic	Consortium GEPs comparison, GE concepts, GE achievements and problems, SALTOpower GE actions

For the discussion, along with the presentation, the participants were asked for their opinions on the presented topics and asked to talk about specific situations where they experienced or witnessed situations of gender discrimination.

From the proposed general GE measures, the participants debated on the more suitable ones to apply to the project, and the conclusion was to carry on organising the dedicated seminars, to apply anonymous questionnaires to the consortium teams, and a smaller

version of it to FTS participants (see section 6), to analyse the gender balance in the project teams and institutions (see section 2), but also in the participants of SALTOpower FTSs, by asking them to identify their gender when registering (applied to FTS#2 and #3, as FTS#1 was held before this GE seminar).

Figure 5.2.1: Online Seminar presentation slide

The seminar video is available on the SALTOpower website and YouTube (see section 7).

5.3 ProM#3 GE Seminar

Table 5.3.1 summarises the ProM#3 GE Seminar. The participants started by attending an EIGE (European Institute for Gender Equality) Webinar, taking advantage of the fact that it would be taking place on the same day as the seminar, and the subject was “Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition”. The webinar explained what GE relates to the energetic transition: 28% of the European energy consumption comes from residential consumption, and that use is affected by gender roles and norms, as women do more household chores.

After the webinar, a presentation was made focusing on the *Rush hour of life*, unconscious bias related to gender, for instance, unconscious bias in the job market and toxic masculinity. Some recent Portuguese news and statistics regarding the gender pay gap were presented, as well as a review of the GE assessment in SALTOpower, Deliverables, and the percentage of T1.4 completion, 25% (Appendix 2).

Table 5.3.1: ProM#3 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#3 GE Seminar
Date	14 November 2023
Project Month	M13
Location/Host	Casa Cordovil, Universidade de Évora, Évora / UÉvora
Presentation	Webinar EIGE Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s SALTOPower technical-administrative support) Célia Peralta (UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion)
Participants	UÉvora, ENEA and DLR SALTOpower teams participating in ProM#3
Number of participants per gender	11 men, 10 women
Duration	150 minutes
Main topic	Webinar EIGE Rush hour of life Unconscious bias Problems and solutions identified - measures to propose to the Consortium

Figure 5.3.1: EIGE Webinar projection during ProM#3 GE Seminar and slide from the presentation

A debate followed the presentation, identifying some problems and possible solutions that researchers found, namely in their work-life balance. It was decided that from these discussions, a document could be prepared with proposals to be presented to the administrations of all the consortium partners (Appendix 7).

5.4 ProM#4 GE Seminar

Table 5.4.1 summarises the ProM#4 GE Seminar. The participants started by answering the SALTOpower GE questionnaire, using a QR code (the questionnaire was also sent by email to allow more team members to answer it). A presentation about the importance of using gender-sensitive language was held - gender-sensitive communication ensures that women and men are treated as persons of equal importance and dignity - followed by an exercise of identifying GE-related errors in a text and how to correct them¹⁴. The presentation ended with the percentage of T1.4 completion, 50% (Appendix 2).

Table 5.4.1: ProM#4 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#4 GE Seminar
Date	5 July 2024
Project Month	M21
Location/Host	Casino Building, Cologne / DLR
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora's SALTOpower technical-administrative support)
Participants	UÉvora, ENEA and DLR SALTOpower teams participating in ProM#4
Number of participants per gender	6 men, 2 women
Duration	30 minutes
Main topic	SALTOpower GE survey Gender-sensitive language

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<https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/toolkits-guides/gender-sensitive-communication/common-challenges-when-using-gender-sensitive-language>

The discussion that followed the presentation focused on the importance of using inclusive language and on the relevance of discussing the topic of GE, which is in itself a positive outcome of the project.

The participants discussed the challenges of gender roles in society and GE in society and their workplaces, recognising the lack of gender balance in their, namely in DLR and ENEA. It is a scientific area where there are few women, but today there is not as much discrimination as there was in the 1980s and 1990s, when there were very few women. Currently, if we find two candidates with the same evaluation and the same motivation, we choose the woman (in cases where this is the underrepresented gender). Although this may lead to a new problem, typical in quota systems: “You got the job just because you are a woman”.

GE discussions raise consciousness for men and women on how to identify situations that sometimes even women are not aware of, like language use, raising awareness and helping to know how to address people, having more respectful communication.

The partners agreed to revise their language to be more inclusive, both in documents and communication channels. ENEA shared the inclusive language guide (as referred to in section 4.1), and it would be important to have this kind of guide in all institutions, both adapted to English and local languages.

The institutions need diversity, and that implies more than just not to discriminate, people need to be included.

Another conclusion is that sexual harassment is on a criminal level, but speaking about it improves understanding and avoids those situations. It is important to promote safe environments for all members to share their experiences and concerns.

Figure 5.4.1: ProM#4 GE Seminar presentation

5.5 ProM#7 GE Seminar

The next GE seminar will be held along with the project’s final meeting, scheduled for the 1st and 2nd of October 2025, in Évora, hosted by UÉvora. Table 5.5.1 summarises the foreseen contents for a presentation and a visit.

Table 5.5.1: ProM#7 GE Seminar summary

GE Seminar	ProM#7 GE Seminar
Date	1 or 2 October 2025
Project Month	M36
Location/Host	University of Évora, Évora / UÉvora
Presentation	Dominique Livreiro (UÉvora’s SALTOPower technical-administrative support) Collaboration: Célia Peralta (UÉvora’s Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion) and ASM Association
Participants	Presentation: UÉvora, ENEA and DLR SALTOpower teams participating in ProM#7 Visit: University of Évora community

Number of participants per gender	
Duration	30 minutes + visit
Main topic	SALTOpower survey results Presentation of T1.4 results Visit to an exhibition on the subject of gender-based violence and domestic violence

In view of preparing this last GE seminar, the UÉvora SALTOpower team, in collaboration with the Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion, is going to propose a partnership with a local non-profit association, Associação Ser Mulher¹⁵, to bring its exhibition “Digitálias¹⁶”, which integrates the work developed in artistic laboratories, as a collective composed of women who are survivors of domestic violence, to the University of Évora. After a presentation regarding Task 1.4 results, including the surveys and their conclusions, the ProM#7 participants will be invited to a guided visit to the exhibition, which will also be opened to the community.

This collaboration will soon be proposed, in the alternative, if the exhibition is not possible to be on display at the University on this date, ProM#7 participants will be invited to visit it at the venue of its display by then, as it has been exhibited in various locations around the city, such as the town hall and the Eugénio de Almeida Foundation.

Figure 5.5.1: Logo of the “Digitálias” exhibition (Associação Ser Mulher) and picture of one of the works on display

6. SURVEYS

The objective of the GE surveys was to understand the perceptions of this topic among project team members and FTSS participants, to receive their opinions and suggestions on what to address in the seminars, and to understand the relevance they consider addressing GE to have, in general and in the context of scientific research.

To this end, a questionnaire was used in the two twinning projects at the UÉvora, SALTOpower and Sol2H2O¹⁷, based on examples of surveys used by partners in these consortia. In order to improve their knowledge of how to develop the questionnaire, the UÉvora technical-administrative team attended an open lecture held at the university.

¹⁵ <https://associacaoosermulher.wordpress.com/about/>

¹⁶ <https://www.instagram.com/digitaliascoletivomulheres/>

¹⁷ Project: 101079305 — Sol2H2O — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

After developing the questionnaire, it was tested in a paper pilot version at the next ProM (Sol2H2O ProM#3). Participants who tested the pilot version suggested that the questions should be answered on a scale of agreement, rather than with “yes and no” answers, as they felt that in some cases the answers would not apply so strictly.

A second version was developed and put into Google Forms format to facilitate its application, both with SALTOpower teams and with FTSs participants, for whom a version without the last three questions was made, as these are questions that concern to working in the project (Appendices 3 and 4).

The questionnaire was then applied, using QR Codes, respectively, in ProMs #4, #5, and #6, and in FTS#2 and #3, so that team members and FTS participants who hadn’t answered before had the chance to do it, advising them to respond only if they had not already done so on a previous occasion. The questionnaires were also sent by email, with the link, in an attempt to increase the number of responses, in order to improve the representativeness of the samples.

It should be noted that the questionnaires are **anonymous**, to allow for unconstrained replies, and took about 5 minutes to fill out. About 50% of the FTSs participants filled in the questionnaire (25 answers from external non-repeated participants), and 56% of the team members (19 answers, taking into account the 34 team members reported in M34, see Table 2.2.2.1). A low representativeness in the number of answers to the questionnaires was defined as Risk RL20 of the project, being reduced by promoting answering the questionnaires on several occasions.

6.1 SALTOpower teams GE Survey

The survey was presented in ProM#4 (after which 9 answers were received), #5 (14 answers), and #6 (19 answers) and sent by email, using a QR code and the link to the Google Forms with the questionnaire.

According to Table 2.2.2.1, the proportion of women in the three partners total is 48%, and 52% of men, which is very similar to the gender of the members who answered the questionnaire: 47.40% women and 52.60% men.

19 team members from the three partners (including young and senior researchers, and other staff) responded to this survey as presented in Appendix 3. This sample size corresponds to a confidence level of 48% and a margin of error of 15.16%¹⁸, meaning that, statistically, this sample is not significant, nevertheless, it allowed for the gathering of useful information.

Some of the answers are analysed in Table 6.1.1.

Table 6.1.1: Teams GE Survey analysis

Question	Answers	Analysis
4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	<p>1 person answered “No” and 4 “Don’t know/won’t answer” (26.4%), although all partners institutions have GEPs. From the people who know the GEP exists, only 47.1% have read it (question 4.1). More dissemination or training is necessary.</p>

¹⁸ <http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>

<p>6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p>	<p>Although most people have not experienced this discrimination, six people reported that they had, and of these, 83.33% are women, but it was in a previous or outside work/study places (question 6.1).</p>
<p>7.1. In upper management positions, are there gender inequalities?</p> <p>(1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (yellow), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>78.9% think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment promotions) for men and women at their work/study organisation (question 7), but 36.8% agree that there are inequalities in top positions.</p>
<p>8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organisation?</p> <p>(1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (yellow), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>Most part of the answers (57.9%) agree, but only 42.1% (question 8.1) know specific measures, referring to (question 8.1.1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> "Part-time" "Parental Leave" "Continuous journey" "Homeoffice flexibility" "Floating hour system" "Flexible work schedules".
<p>10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?</p> <p>(1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (yellow), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>57.9% of the people did not feel this discrimination, and the person who answered "I partially agree" is a man.</p>
<p>11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p>	<p>15 people said they don't often hear or say sexist comments, 1 man answered "yes", and 3 people answered "don't know/won't answer", which may indicate a lack of awareness about what can be considered sexist comments.</p>
<p>12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (yellow)</p>	<p>6 people answered "yes" (50% women and 50% men), in a previous or outside work/study places (question 12.1), and 4 people answered "don't know/won't answer", which may indicate a lack</p>

		<p>of awareness about what can be considered gender discrimination.</p> <p>3 people (2 women and 1 man) described the situations:</p> <p>“Women not placed in positions due to the intent of having children in coming near future”</p> <p>“Not selected for an internship because the working environment is mostly men, and the company does not feel comfortable selecting a female despite being the top candidate on qualifications level”</p> <p>“Sometimes, women are not seen as so good professionals as men”.</p>
13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?	<p>68.4%</p> <p>26.3%</p> <p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>Most people answered “no”, but 5 people (60% men and 40% women) answered “yes”, 2 referring that it was “at their current place of work/study” (questions 13.1 and 13.1.1):</p> <p>“From teachers to students”</p> <p>“Professor's harassment of student”.</p>
14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organisation?	<p>47.4%</p> <p>52.6%</p> <p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>Almost half (47.4%) of the people do not know how to report a complaint in these situations.</p>
15. In your opinion, is it important to address gender equality issues in research projects such as SALTOpower?	<p>89.5%</p> <p>● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer</p>	<p>89.5% agree that it is important to address GE in research projects, and the same proportion agrees that there is gender equality in the SALTOpower project (question 16).</p>

6.2 FTSS GE Survey

The survey was presented in FTS#2 (after which 19 answers were received), and FTS#3 (25 answers) and sent by email, using a QR code and the link to the Google Forms with the questionnaire.

The proportion of women in the FTSS is 35% and 36%, and 64% and 65% of men, which is very similar to the gender of the persons who answered the questionnaire: 36% women and 64% men.

25 FTS non-repeated external participants from the two editions (including young and senior researchers, and other staff) responded to this survey as presented in Appendix 4. This sample size corresponds to a confidence level of 51% and a margin of error of 14.13%. Statistically, this sample is not significant, but it allowed for a brief analysis, Table 6.2.1.

Table 6.2.1: FTSSs GE Survey analysis

Question	Answers	Analysis
<p>4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?</p>	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	<p>24% of participants answered “Don’t know/won’t answer”, and from the 60% participants who know the GEP exists, only 13.6% have read it (question 4.1). More dissemination or training is necessary.</p>
<p>5.1. In your opinion, is there gender equality in society in general?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p> ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 </p>	<p>60% of the participants consider that there is gender equality in society in general, but only 12% (question 5.2) consider that there is no equality in their current work/study organisation.</p>
<p>6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?</p>	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	<p>10 participants, from which 80% are women, have experienced gender discrimination, 2 of these women referred (question 6.1) that it is in their current work/study organisation. 12% of the participants answered “Don’t know/won’t answer”.</p>
<p>7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organisation?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p> ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 </p>	<p>52% of participants think that there are equal opportunities, but also 52% agree that there are inequalities in top positions (question 7.1).</p>
<p>9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p> ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 </p>	<p>32% of the participants agree that women and men are assigned different tasks.</p>

<p>10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents?</p> <p>(1 means “I completely disagree”, 2 means “I disagree partially”, 3 means “I don’t agree or disagree”, 4 means “I partially agree” and 5 means “I completely agree”)</p>	<p>Legend: 1 (blue), 2 (red), 3 (orange), 4 (green), 5 (purple)</p>	<p>2 participants felt this discrimination, one man and one woman.</p>
<p>11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (orange)</p>	<p>28% of participants often hear (question 11.1) sexist comments.</p>
<p>12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (orange)</p>	<p>8 people answered “yes” (62.50% women), including 2 women in the current work/study place (question 12.1). 7 people answered “don’t know/won’t answer”, which may indicate a lack of awareness about what can be considered gender discrimination.</p> <p>4 participants described the situations:</p> <p>“Position won by women, but in the end, they were not included because they were planning to have children in the near future”</p> <p>“Various but not so critical”</p> <p>“Women were automatically assigned subordinate tasks like doing a protocol”</p> <p>“Not being heard when I made a comment and when someone said the same thing, it was heard and considered”.</p>
<p>13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?</p>	<p>Legend: Yes (blue), No (red), Don't know/ won't answer (orange)</p>	<p>9 people (55.56% women) answered “yes”, 2 referring that it was “at their current place of work/study”, identifying four situations (questions 13.1 and 13.1.1):</p> <p>“Sexual harassment of interns by workshop employees”</p> <p>“People assume I need/search for a partner just because I am a young-looking woman without knowing anything about me”</p> <p>“Sexist comments and looks”</p> <p>“Professors harassing students”.</p>

<p>14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organisation?</p>	<p> ● Yes ● No ● Don't know/ won't answer </p>	<p>Just over half (52%) of the participants know how to report a complaint in these situations.</p>
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7. GE IN THE SALTOPower COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

The GE theme has also been addressed in the project's communication channels (see D5.2), as detailed below, celebrating International Women's Day, publishing about the seminars, introducing the team members, and sharing GE campaigns. Until the end of the project, other releases will be made, for instance, the #EndGenderStereotypes campaign was announced in the last newsletter and can also be shared on social media, and the survey results will be available on the website.

7.1 Meet our team

The *Meet our team* heading allowed introducing the SALTOpower partners' teams, while also giving visibility to women, both scientists and other employees working in the project. It was published both on the project's social networks (Instagram and LinkedIn) and newsletters. This heading included a picture of the team member and four short-answer questions, one of which regarding GE: "According to your experience and the Gender Equality seminars promoted at SALTOpower, what can be improved in this area?". The answers received are presented in Table 7.1.1.

Table 7.1.1: "Meet our team" GE question and answers

<p>According to your experience and the Gender Equality seminars promoted at SALTOpower, what can be improved in this area?</p>	<p>"Related to the gender equality plan, I believe it is essential for women to understand that CSP, as a research topic, is not exclusive to men and can be integrated by anyone, regardless of gender. Increased dissemination of information from SALTOpower and other related projects can capture more attention and encourage broader participation."</p>
	<p>"Statistics show that there is still a lack of gender equality in Portugal and Europe, for example, concerning salaries earned, so it is important to continue to address this issue in all contexts, as it is a culturally-rooted issue. In the case of research, top positions are more difficult for women to fill, and in the seminars we've already organised with the project teams, we've discussed ideas on how to improve."</p>
	<p>"Although Gender Equality has its point and pertinence, I strongly believe that even more important is to support young researchers during this "rush hour of life". Being myself in the very middle of it, and considering how competitive R&D is these days, I find it to be extremely challenging to compatible work, family and self-development. One always gets the impression that we are lacking beyond leading, sometimes, to some sort of anxiety and desperation. To worsen the situation, we are called to fully and actively participate in multiple tasks at the same time, such as R&D development, proposal preparation, project management, student supervision, etc. I believe that a more focused and organised R&D, more suitable to the needs and availability of each person, could have a tremendous positive impact on the attraction of young researchers and technicians, creating a fulfilling environment which could actually raise people's commitment and engagement in their work."</p>
	<p>"I believe that the SALTOpower Gender Equality Seminars are an essential contribution to demystifying some of the preconceptions that many people make. In general, I think it's important for research teams to have these moments to talk about emerging issues such as Gender Equality, because it's these small contributions that have the possibility of helping to change the current paradigm, taking into account the location and specific tasks of each area."</p>
	<p>"The promotion of this discussion, alone, is already an important step to put GE questions on the</p>

Agenda, also to show that these questions affect both genders.”

Six team members responded to this short interview, as presented in Figures 7.1.1, 7.3.1, 7.4.1 and 7.4.2.

Figure 7.1.1: Meet our team publications on SALTOpower Instagram

7.2 Website

In the SALTOpower website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/>), the WP leaders and the team members are presented (Figure 7.2.1), news referring to the GE seminars (mentions to seminars along ProM and a dedicated news to the online GE seminar¹⁹- Figure 7.2.2), and to the leadership training (see section 4.1) are published (Figure 7.2.3). The online GE seminar video on the SALTOpower YouTube is also available through the website²⁰.

¹⁹ <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/gender-equality-seminar-1-2/>

²⁰ <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#videos>

Figure 7.2.1: SALTOpower WP leaders and team members on the website

Gender Equality Seminar #1

16/10/2023

Gender Equality assessment in SALTOpower

The SALTOpower project partners met online on the 16th October in a Seminar organized by the University of Évora, within the scope of the coordination of the SALTOpower Project – European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications (HEUROPE GA 101079303), of the Renewable Energy Chair, with the collaboration from the Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion. The importance of approaching gender issues and some related concepts was analyzed and discussed, such as: the glass ceiling effect, the cement ceiling effect and the Matilda effect. Positive measures and advances in terms of gender equity and some problems that still persist were also topics of discussion.

The Plans for Gender Equality of the three partner institutions, UÉvora (project leader), DLR (German Aerospace Center) and ENEA (Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile), were compared and the strategy for monitoring and evaluating the measures to be implemented in the SALTOpower project were defined. In the next project meetings, the partners will address this topic again.

Figure 7.2.2: News about the online GE seminar on the SALTOpower website

**Workshop de
Liderança na
Cátedra de
Energias
Renováveis**

12/05/2025

Figure 7.2.3: News about the Leadership training on the SALTOpower website (Portuguese version)

Survey results, including the ones regarding GE (see section 6), will be published on the website, always ensuring anonymity and complying with data protection rules.

7.3 Newsletters

The SALTOpower newsletters²¹ included the *Meet our teams* headings (Figure 7.3.1; newsletters #3, #4 and #6), news (Figure 7.3.2) and video of the online GE seminar (newsletter #2), references to GE seminars along project meetings (newsletters #2 and #6), news about the leadership training (newsletter #11), and the EU campaign #EndGenderStereotypes²² (newsletter #12, Figure 7.3.3).

Figure 7.3.1: *Meet our team* in SALTOpower newsletters

Figure 7.3.2: News about the online GE seminar in the SALTOpower newsletter

Figure 7.3.3: #EndGenderStereotypes campaign in the SALTOpower newsletter

²¹ <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#newsletters>

²² https://end-gender-stereotypes.campaign.europa.eu/index_en

7.4 Social networks

In SALTOpower social networks, Instagram²³ and LinkedIn²⁴, GE-related publications were made regarding *Meet our team* (Figures 7.4.1 and 7.4.2), the leadership training, mobilities, International Women’s Day (Figures 7.4.3), and GE seminars (Figures 7.4.4). The online GE seminar video is available on SALTOpower YouTube²⁵.

Figure 7.4.1: *Meet our team* publications on SALTOpower Instagram

²³ https://www.instagram.com/saltopower_heurope/

²⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/saltopower/>

²⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RmNPat3cTlg&list=PLtmABrST4ziqAA53sa4w-vuoa3RDqRFDG&index=5>

Figure 7.4.2: Meet our team publications on SALTOpower LinkedIn

Figure 7.4.3: International Women's Day post and story in SALTOpower Instagram

Figure 7.4.4: EIGE webinar in ProM#3 story in SALTOpower Instagram

7.5 Project video

The project video was published in SALTOpower YouTube²⁶ and website, and it presents SALTOpower, with interviews with all WP leaders, one per partner (Figure 7.5.1), which means that there are no interviews with women in the video, although female technicians from the team who work at the Research Infrastructure do appear (Figure 7.5.2).

Figure 7.5.1: Project video interviews with WP leaders

Figure 7.5.2: SALTOpower RI technician in the project video

8. GENDER EQUALITY ACTION BARRIERS

The main barriers to implementing the Gender Equality task in SALTOpower were to define concrete actions to take, and a general lack of interest in the subject, because although it is commonly agreed that there should be equal rights and duties between men and women, measures are not always well accepted, and events almost always focus on the same general topics, leading to a devaluation of the subject.

²⁶ <https://youtu.be/YBW9lcAKtLQ>

Albeit having an excellent relationship with the University of Évora's Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion, it only has one employee, who divides her work between GE and other types of inclusion, both for workers and university students.

Another difficulty is obtaining statistical representativeness in the surveys conducted, as the teams and participants in the FTSs are relatively small populations, in addition to the aforementioned lack of interest.

The difficulties in collecting data and participating in debates may also be related to the sensitivity of the topic, even though the anonymity of the surveys was guaranteed, which is impossible to achieve in seminar discussions.

The project timeframe is limited for profound structural changes, given the 36-month timeframe, but the Task 1.4 (WP1) proposed objective was achieved: *to monitor and enhance Gender Equality measures and aspects*, as detailed in the Conclusions, and actions to recommend were learned, both to propose to partner institutions (see section 9), and for upcoming projects, it would be important to include GE actions more frequently in scientific projects, in addition to declaring the existence of an institutional GEP. There should be systematic inclusion of gender indicators in scientific and management reports. Another good practice is the integration of gender-themed seminars into regular technical project meetings, promoting horizontal participation.

One suggestion for monitoring gender proportion at events is to ask for gender information when participants register, using forms to ensure data confidentiality (as SALTOpower did in the FTSs, but not in the symposiums), since gender is something with which each person identifies and cannot be inferred by observing people/names on attendance lists.

9. MEASURES TO PROPOSE TO THE INSTITUTIONAL ADMINISTRATIONS

As a result of Gender Equality's assessment actions in the SALTOpower project, a list of measures to propose to the administrations of UÉvora, ENEA, and DLR is presented, in view of further improving the inclusion of all in these institutions. Some of the measures mentioned are already being implemented by some of the consortium partners' institutions, but are a proposal to the other institutions, and in some cases, it has been found that they are not known to all employees, like all the work-life balance measures already implemented.

1. To include gender data for all employees in the Human Resources database, so that at any moment, a gender balance of the institution can be assessed;
2. Awareness campaigns and training regarding Gender Equality and gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, are needed, so that people can better identify and report these situations, without being afraid of retaliation;
3. Reporting channels or who to approach in situations of gender-based violence or sexual harassment are not well-known to all employees, more dissemination of this information is necessary;
4. Since the use of inclusive language is essential for equal communication, institutions must have guides, in the local language and in English, which should be disseminated or training provided to employees, so that institutional and scientific documents are not discriminatory, as well as the institutional communication;
5. Work-life balance measures already proposed should be effectively implemented and disseminated among the employees;
6. Childcare services, summer camps available for longer periods, covering more age groups and with more places and day care centres for elderly cohabiting parents,

provided by the institutions or in partnership with them, at affordable prices, would facilitate employees' work-life balance;

7. Increasing women's visibility as researchers, technicians, etc., with promotional videos and school visits;
8. In the case of educational institutions, include gender equality issues in more study programmes;
9. Strengthen Gender Equality offices so that they can carry out more activities and implement/disseminate measures more easily;
10. Promote the inclusion of Gender Equality measures and discussions in more scientific projects;
11. To offer part-time positions so that people can have a better work-life balance and flexible schedules;
12. To make packages that include families when a researcher goes into mobility available;
13. Welcoming people who arrive at institutions, using measures such as the "Living Amenities Facility" that SALTOpower has implemented;
14. The interruption, whether due to parenthood, illness, or any other reason, must not affect the researchers' (and other staff) careers, so their assessment system, for example, should take this into account;
15. Safety clothes are almost always purchased in "men's sizes", not suitable for all sizes of men and women, and may even make them less secure. Purchases more suitable for all workers should be taken into account;
16. With regard to occupational diseases and accidents at work, as well as gender-related health issues, institutions should take gender into account, promoting health for women employees, doing gender-related workplace risk assessments, and considering sex-specific differences in health outcomes, disease prevalence, and treatment responses.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The SheFigures 2024 report²⁷ shows that there is still some way to go in the European Union towards Gender Equality. In the case of countries represented in the SALTOpower consortium, this report highlights that there have been many improvements, and there is still a need for:

- in Germany, further efforts are needed to increase the proportion of women in science and education, researchers in the business enterprise sector, women in top positions and submitting patent applications;
- in Italy, further actions are needed to increase outputs for women researchers, particularly as authors of publications and patent inventors;
- in Portugal, further efforts are needed to increase the proportion of women among researchers in the business enterprise sector and to increase women's opportunities for career advancement and participation in decision-making.

²⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/592260>

In that report, a “She Figures Index” was developed as a tool to measure the extent to which EU member states have achieved GE in the European Research Area, and the results for the countries represented in the SALTOpower consortium are presented in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1: *She Figures Index* in Portugal, Italy and Germany

The surveys applied in SALTOpower allowed access to some GE perceptions, and evidence that more awareness is needed. The debates in themselves were important, getting to know the teams better, creating an environment where everyone can express themselves, and empowering women in the team.

The conclusions for each of the five recommended action topics are detailed below.

10.1 Work-Life Balance and Organisational Culture

SALTOpower implemented initiatives promoting well-being and quality of life (‘Living Amenities Facility’), which aimed to improve work-life balance, particularly relevant for female researchers.

More information about the conciliation measures that exist in the institutions is needed, as the surveys showed that only 42.1% (project teams) and 36% (FTS participants) know some measures, and the ones they referred to know were quite limited compared to those that are referred to in GEPs. This may also indicate, in addition to a lack of awareness, that these measures, although considered in theory, are not actually being implemented.

The SALTOpower GE seminars and the debates in themselves were productive, and talking about the topic is one of the goals achieved, as mentioned in one of the suggestions in a survey, “Speak openly and loudly about this topic”. The debates and the GEP comparison lead to the proposals that can be presented to the UÉvora, ENEA and DLR administrations (see section 9).

10.2 Gender Balance in Leadership and Decision-making

The gender balance analysis showed that in UÉvora, there were more women working than men, but in top positions, the proportion is the opposite. In ENEA and DLR, there are fewer women employees than men, and it is worse in top positions.

In SALTOpower teams, overall, there was an improvement in the gender balance, although there are more men researchers and more women in “other staff”, and the top positions (WP leaders) are now occupied by men.

The leadership training held in UÉvora was a good practice action that can be replicated in other projects.

10.3 Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression

In recruitment, priority should be given to the underrepresented gender in the department that is recruiting, in cases where there is equal classification in the selection criteria.

One of the main conclusions of the seminar discussions was the difficulty of career progression, which is generally accentuated in the case of women, due to parenthood or caring for other people (descendants, ascendants, etc.). Measures should be taken to compensate for these absences, as well as absences due to illness, such as an adjustment in the classification systems for researchers.

In Portugal, FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, the Portuguese Ministry of Education and Science department that evaluates and funds scientific research activities, created the RESTART²⁸ program, promoting gender equality and opportunities through the competitive funding of individual R&D projects, in all scientific fields, when carried out by researchers who have recently taken parental leave, including adoption.

10.4 Integration of the Gender Dimension into Research and Teaching Content

It is definitely important to include the gender dimension in research, and the SALTOpower survey showed that 89.5% of the respondents agreed that it was important to address GE in SALTOpower.

UÉvora, as a teaching institution, already includes this topic in some of its study programmes, and the GEP indicates that it intends to extend it to more courses, which is extremely important in the current context of increasing gender-based violence among young people.

10.5 Measures against Gender-based Violence, including Sexual harassment

Gender-based harassment at work is a problem within the area of research and innovation in higher education environments²⁹, and the SALTOpower surveys refer several times to student harassment by teachers.

Furthermore, in both surveys, approximately half of the respondents said they did not know what to do or who to reach to report gender-based violence. There is a need to publicise the reporting channels available in the institutions. It was also mentioned in the seminar discussions that in many cases reports are not made, either because of fear of negative consequences for the victims or because of the perception that the perpetrators face very few consequences, namely if they are in top positions.

The SALTOpower GE surveys also showed that gender based discrimination and harassment are more often felt or witnessed by women (60% and 56%).

10.6 Other relevant topics

Although women generally show more interest in the GE topic, as was perceived in some of the seminars, with almost only women participating in the GE events attended by the technical-administrative team, and it was also a result of the UÉvora perception report, in the SALTOpower surveys, this was not verified. The gender proportions of respondents are very similar to the proportion of participants' gender, which indicates equal interest from both genders, albeit reduced, in general, given the low number of responses.

SALTOpower suggests strengthening institutional equality policies, integrating gender into more projects, and continuing to hold seminars and training sessions on Gender Equality.

²⁸ <https://www.fct.pt/en/financiamento/programas-de-financiamento/outros-apoios/programa-restart/>

²⁹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, *2025 report on gender equality in the EU*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2838/5262357>

11. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The *Data Management Plan* describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in a project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action>	Project folder
4	Deliverables Acceptance Plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SALTOPOWER.14-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
5	Deliverables acceptance Checklist	Project Folder
6	Data Management Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_05-05-2023_v_2>	Project Folder
7	GE seminar in ProM#2 <Gender Equality Plan Évora University SALTOPOWER>	Project Folder
8	GE online seminar <Gender Equality Seminar_october23>	Project Folder
9	GE seminar in ProM#3 <SALTOpower_WP1_Gender Equality_november23>	Project Folder
10	GE seminar in ProM#4 <SALTOpower_PM_4_Day4>	Project Folder
11	Gender Equality Plans folder <Gender Equality Plans>	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: GE SEMINARS PRESENTATIONS

- **ProM#2 GE Seminar**

European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications
GA Number: 101079303
European Research Executive Agency REA-C3

Funded by the European Union

WORK PACKAGE 1: Coordination

UÉvora, 09.05.2023

Gender Equality Plan Évora University

Meeting SALTOpower
ENEA Casaccia Research Centre
Date: 09.-11.May.2023

Funded by the European Union

Célia Peralta
Office for Gender Equality and Inclusion at Évora University

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA
GABINETE PARA A IGUALDADE
DE GÉNERO E INCLUSÃO

References

The Human Rights and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) defined by the 2030 Agenda, in particular, SDG 5 - Gender Equity and SDG 10 - Reducing Inequalities.

Additionally, this plan closely follows the underlying vision of the programmatic cycle launched by the National Strategy for Equality and Non-Discrimination (ENIND) 2018-2030

- The elaboration of the Gender Equality Plan at the University of Évora followed closely the international guidelines in this regard, namely, the ones made by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)
- “Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool”

- **Transversal areas:**
 - Awareness raising, training and capacity building
 - Organizational culture, communication, and language
 - Follow-up and monitoring
- The action plan **focuses specifically on 5 areas:**
 - Work/study articulation, personal and family life
 - leadership and decision-making
 - Recruitment, selection, career development and academic progression
 - Gender mainstreaming in research and education
 - Measures against discrimination and gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

Gender Equality Plan Évora University

A1.: AWARENESS RAISING, TRAINING AND CAPACITY BUILDING

O1: Contribute, through awareness raising, training and capacity building, for the elimination of all forms of discrimination based on sex and promote gender equality

Specific Objectives	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE1.1: Encourage reflection on gender issues, namely stereotypes, preconceptions, discrimination, unconscious biases, and gender violence	M1: Conducting an awareness campaign in institutional media, composed of multi-format actions (newsletters, webpage, and social networks...) -10 pieces of sensitization/year	Internal and external community	2022/23	No. of Actions Performed No. of parts produced/ support	Gabgual DivCom EArtes
OE1.2: Provide the University with an annual training and capacity building plan on gender issues, with a view to integrating the Internal Vocational Training Plan of the University of Évora	M2: Elaboration of an annual training plan on the themes of equality, equity, and diversity - 1 plan/year	DRH	annually	1 plan produced	Gabgual DRH
OE1.3: Raise awareness and empower the academic community in order to recognize and deal with situations of sex-based discrimination which creates feelings of injustice and objective situations of inequality	M3: Conducting training actions aimed at differentiated audiences - 4 training actions/year	PDI PND NI DIR EST	2022/23	No. of Actions Performed No. of Participants/Action	Gabgual DRH AAUE
OE1.4: Contribute, through scientific knowledge, to informed reflection and debate, having in mind awareness raising and the elimination of gender-based discrimination and defining solutions and policies that address the gender dimension	M4: Cooperation with national, regional, and local authorities, ONGs, civil society agents and local communities in the reflection, debate and definition of solutions and policies that include the production of scientific knowledge around gender issues - 4 cooperation initiatives/year	Civil society Local communities	2022/23	No. of cooperation initiatives undertaken No. of participants/ activity No. of new contracts/ partnership formalized	Gabgual DivCom UOs IFA R&D Unit AAUE National, regional, and local authorities ONG Civil society Local communities

Gender Equality Plan Évora University

A2.: ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE, COMMUNICATION AND LANGUAGE

O2: Deconstruct stereotypes in the organizational culture, eliminate discrimination in language, and achieve equal treatment in institutional communication

Specific goals	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE2.1: Contribute to the affirmation of the University of Évora as an institution aligned with the values of equality, equity, and diversity	M5: Streamlining of a virtual channel for equality plan discussion and gender-related content	Internal and external community	2022/23, scheduled to start in March 2022	No. of updates/electronic file/month No. Accesses/month	Gabgual DivCom
OE2.2: Welcoming new members of the academic community (PDI, PNDNI, EST) into an organizational culture explicitly committed to the values of equality, equity, and diversity	M6: Inclusion of explicit references to UEvora's commitment to the values of equality, equity, and diversity for inclusion in institutional reception documents made available when hiring human resources and entering students	The academic community	June 2022	1 reference in the "Welcome Manual" 1 reference in the "Guide to Academic Proceedings" 1 reference in the "International Student Guide and in Ability>Welcome Guide"	Gabgual DivCom DRH GAE/Sac
OE2.3: Disseminate the use of gender-sensitive language by internal services with a view to adopting good practices for the use of a language that promotes equality in Public Administration	M7: Preparation and promotion of a guide to gender-sensitive language for use in services	University Services	December 2022	1 document produced	Gabgual DivCom
OE2.4: Reinforce the use of gender-sensitive language and achieve equal treatment in the contents of institutional documents and in content oriented to internal and external communication	M8: Revision and rectification of institutional documents, printed documents, forms, and tender notices in order of adopting inclusive language in the contents of institutional documents -minimum of 2 documents/service M9: Application of gender sensitive language in internal and external communication (e.g., FB, webpage, newsletters, posters, flyers...) - 100% of the parts produced	Executives People assigned to the Services DivCom	December 2022 January 2023	No. of documents indicated for review No. of reviewed documents No. of conforming parts/No. of parts produced	Gabgual DivCom Gabgual DivCom

Gender Equality Plan Évora University

A3.: WORK/STUDY ARTICULATION, PERSONAL AND FAMILY LIFE

O3: WORK/STUDY ARTICULATION, PERSONAL AND FAMILY LIFE

Specific goals	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE3.1: To overcome the difficulties of reconciling childcare and academic life, in order to enable/increase the participation of the academic community in events promoted by the University	M10: Development of a response for the care/occupation of children when conducting scientific events or other extraordinary events that occur in university spaces outside the work/ school period M11: Enlargement and introduction of improvements in procedures with entities active in the area of family and personal life support - minimum of 3 new or revised protocols/year	The academic community The academic community	March 2023 2022/23	Launch of the response No. of requests for use of the response registered in 2023 No. of uses No. of new protocols No. of reviewed protocols	Gabgual SASUE Technical Services UOs Pool of Volunteers Gabgual DRH
OE3.2: Promote initiatives to disseminate information on internal rights and practices in the field of work/ study/family/personal life articulation, aimed at the various internal publics	M12: Publication of information notes on rights at work and internal practices relating to the conciliation of personal and family life with professional and student life - 3 notes/year	PDI PNDNI DIR EST	2022/23	No. of notes published No. of views	Gabgual DivCom
OE3.3: Valuing rational time management that preserves the limits between working time and personal time, ensures the existence of rest periods and the right to disconnect	M13: Preparation of explicit guidelines for the rational management of time by workers and students, which allows the boundaries between working time and personal time to be established, ensuring the existence of rest periods and the right to disconnect, aimed at the various internal audiences	The academic community	semiannual, starting in September 2022	1 guiding document with Good Practices	Gabgual DRH UOs Pedagogical Councils Scientific Councils General Board Senate AAUE

A4: LEADING AND DECIDING

O4: Fostering equal representation of women and men in management and leadership positions

Specific goals	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE4.1: Ensure the balanced representation of women and men in management and leadership roles, pursuant to Law No. 26/2019	M14: Monitoring the balanced representation of women and men in management and leadership positions, in accordance with the law	The academic community	2022/23, starting in December 2022	Construction of an Indicator associated with the National Goal for Gender Equality, for inclusion in the "IJE em números" portfolio	Gabigual DRH Information Technology Services
	M15: Incorporation of a checkbox in the list submission forms for the election of collegiate bodies	The academic community	2022/23, starting at the next electoral act	Existence of a checkbox in the list proposition forms	GPGQ Gabigual DRH Electoral Commissions
OE4.2: Raise awareness of the academic community for the promotion of full equality of access to and participation in power and decision-making structures	M16: Carrying out awareness-raising actions to stimulate the balanced representation of women and men on the lists for the elections of the governing bodies.	The academic community	2023/23	No. of awareness-raising actions Scope of awareness-raising actions	Gabigual Div-Com
OE4.3: Fostering the entrepreneurial attitude and female leadership	-1 awareness-raising action/electoral act M17: Conducting a mentoring program with women who stand out/stand out in the exercise of functions in leadership positions (role model) - 2 mentoring activities/year	Women students, faculty members and researchers	2022/23	No. of mentoring activities performed. No. of participants	Gabigual Div-Com AAUE DICZE Alumni
OE4.4: Motivating and empowering the student community for the importance of the equal occupation of top management and leadership positions	M18: Workshops on the themes of argumentation, assertiveness, leadership, negotiation, and interpersonal relations, sensitive to gender differences - 2 workshops/year	Student community	2022/23	No. of workshops held	Gabigual SEC-Psi GAE/SAc AAUE DICZE

A5: RECRUITMENT, SELECTION, CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ACADEMIC PROGRESSION

O5: Promote gender equality in recruitment, selection, career development and academic progression and contribute to the elimination of gender stereotypes associated with certain positions and areas of knowledge

Specific goals	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE5.1: Integrate the gender perspective in the recruitment and personnel selection processes	M19: Production of a Gender-Sensitive Recruitment and Progression Guide, with codes of conduct and good practices that eliminate the risk of gender bias in recruitment and selection processes	DRH Selection juries	December 2022	1 guide produced	Gabigual DRH
	M20: Carrying out awareness-raising actions on gender bias in recruitment and selection processes based on the Gender-Sensitive Recruitment and Progression Guide	DRH IJE and PHEBE involved in recruitment and selection juries	2022/23	No. of Actions Performed No. of Participants/Action	Gabigual DRH
OE5.2: Incorporate the gender perspective in the design and implementation of evaluation models and career development opportunities	M21: Reflection and discussion on the effects of gender in people evaluation processes - 2 working meetings/year	PHEBE PDI	2022/23	No. of meetings held No. of participants No. of recommendations elaborated	Gabigual DRH
	M22: Proposal to introduce criteria in the regulation for the evaluation of faculty members and research staff that allow mitigating the effects of shortfalls in scientific production in exceptional situations (e.g. COVID-19 Pandemic, parenthood, illness, ...) - 2 working meetings/year	PDI	2022/23	No. of meetings held No. of recommendations elaborated	Gabigual IIFA IUCs Research Faculty Members
	M23: Proposal to incorporate a weighting factor that discriminates positively in the selection for international mobility missions faculty members, researchers and researchers who have been fathers or mothers for less than 2 years	PDI	2022/23	Weighting Factor Proposal	Gabigual IIFA IUCs
OE5.3: Deconstructing gender stereotypes associated with professions and scientific areas	M24: Creation of a conversion program focused on the deconstruction of gender stereotypes (STEAM, education, social sciences, health...), conducted by professionals and students of the under-represented sex in the identified areas, aimed at students of basic and secondary school. 2 actions/year	Children and young people in basic and secondary education	Biannual	No. of Actions Number of children and young people participating in the sessions	Gabigual Div-Com IUCs IIFA RBD Unit AAUE

A6: RESEARCH AND TEACHING

O6: Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

Specific goals	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OE6.1: Encourage gender studies and scientific projects in the thematic area of gender, supporting the dissemination of their results	M25: Launch of an annual semi-open call (with predefined themes) for internship/dissertation/thesis/project realization with reception at Gabigual	Student Investigators	annual, with the launch and collection of expressions of interest between May and September of each year	1 Disclosed Call No. of applications received No. of studies and projects	Gabigual IFFA Schools AAUE
OE6.2: Encouraging and supporting under-represented sexes to register patents	M26: Holding Workshops to explore the patenting process for inventions originating from research activities - 2 annual workshops	Investigators	2022/23	No. of workshops No. of Patent/Gender Registrations	Gabigual IFFA SCC
OE6.3: Disseminate and encourage scientific production in the field of gender studies	M27: Creation of videocasts to present UÉvora's recent scientific production in the field of gender studies - every 3 months	The academic community Civil Society	2022/23	No. videocasts No. of views	DICZE Gabigual IFFA RBD Unit
	M28: Award of a research award of excellence in the field of gender studies in collaboration with an organization outside the Unit	PDI EST	biannual, starting in December 2022	1 Prize attribution	DivCom Gabigual RBD Unit External sponsorship (to be defined)
	M29: Recommendation for publication by the Press of the University of Évora of reference/excellence works produced in the area of gender studies at the University of Évora	Acting PDI PDI in Retirement age situation Alumni	biannual, starting in December 2022	Publication of 1 work	Gabigual Press of the University of Évora
OE6.4: Integrate gender studies in the formative offer	M30: Presentation to the Governments of Schools of the proposal to introduce a transversal UC for the elaboration of a FUC in gender studies	Scientific Board Schools Executives	June 2023	Preparation of FUC	Gabigual Schools RBD Unit
OE6.5: Promoting parity in research teams	M31: Recommendation of minimum representation level in the proportion of 1/2 of people of each sex in the composition of project funding application teams	Investigators	June 2022	Preparation of 1 recommendation M/F ratio in candidate project teams	Gabigual IFFA SCC RBD Unit

A7: GENDER DISCRIMINATION AND VIOLENCE, INCLUDING SEXUAL HARASSMENT

O7: Contribute to the eradication of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

Specific Objectives	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OEF.1: Achieving fair treatment that recognizes gender identity in the university's internal personal register	M32: Creation of a standardized name and gender change procedure in the internal university documentation	SAC - Academic Services IT services	July 2022	1 procedure protocolized	Gabigual SAC - Academic Services IT services
OEF.2: Raise awareness through the arts for the prevention and eradication of gender discrimination and violence	M33: Promoting awareness-raising actions through arts aimed at preventing gender-based violence and publicizing services capable of helping in the event of violence or risk situations - 2 awareness actions/year	The academic community	biannual	No. of actions carried out annually No. of participants in the actions	Gabigual SEC-Psi AALJE School of Arts NEI
OEF.3: Creating responses to report and support victims of harassment who are likely to engage in gender-based violence	M34: Developing a code of good conduct for preventing and combating gender-based violence, including sexual harassment	The academic community	December 2022	Published code	Gabigual SEC-Psi GAE/SAC
	M35: Creation of a virtual space for reporting situations of discrimination or harassment of any nature, under confidentiality	The academic community	June 2023	1 virtual space created	Gabigual Ethics Committee SEC-Psi GAE/SAC IT services
	M36: Promotion of the introduction of specialized service of response and assistance to the victim of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in partnership with external entity	The academic community	December 2023	Created Service	Gabigual Ethics Committee SEC-Psi GAE/SAC External entity (to be designated)

A8.: FOLLOW-UP AND MONITORING

O8: Improve data collection and compilation systems to monitor and deepen institutional gender diagnosis

Specific Objectives	Measures	Target-Group	Execution	Indicators	Entities Responsible
OES.1: Continuously monitor the climate of equality, equity, and diversity in the University of Évora	M37: Construction of an instrument to measure the perception of the climate of equality, equity and diversity in the institution and dissemination of results through an annual report	The academic community	2022/23	Quiz based on gamification, created, and made available online with permanent data collection	Gabigual IT services DivCom
OES.2: Document accurate, gender-disaggregated and gender-sensitive statistical data to track the impact of policies and reveal areas for further intervention	M38: Promotion of the continuous collection of statistical data and information management, disaggregated by sex, in all research activities	Services	2022/23	Gender-disaggregated statistical data maps	Gabigual EPD IFFA SCC Services R&D Unit
OES.3: Update the diagnosis on the gender equality situation at the University of Évora based on indicators for equality	M39: Production of an annual report with objective and disaggregated information, for an in-depth knowledge of the gender equality situation of the entire academic community	Internal and external community	annually	Report produced and distributed	Gabigual
OES.4: Review and update measures for the promotion of gender equality to be included in the next University of Évora Gender Equality Plan	M40: Outline of corrective measures and new measures to integrate the next plan	Gabigual	December 2023	Internal report produced	Gabigual

MEETING, ENEA Casaccia Research Centre - Rome 9.-11.May.2023

WP1 TASK DESCRIPTION

LEAD BENEFICIARY: UEVORA

Task 1.4: Gender Profile (Leader: UEVORA; Participants: ENEA, DLR) M1-M36

This task aims at the development and implementation of questionnaires, monitoring procedures and enhancement strategies aiming Gender equality in the access to research and technical-administrative positions in the Consortium institutions. Grounded on the individual experience of the female participants in the project, Gender equality measures – as described in Section 1.1 – will be discussed and presented in 4 dedicated Seminars alongside Project Meetings and hosted, in turns, by Widening and TOP partners;

The description and assessment of Gender Equality measures will be presented in a dedicated D1.6

● **Online GE Seminar**

European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications
GA Number: 101079303
European Research Executive Agency REA.C3

SALTOpower

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA DLR Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt German Aerospace Center ENEC

MS

Funded by the European Union

Gender Equality Seminar

16.10.2023

16.10.2023 2

Structure

Permission to record

INTRODUCTION CONCEPTS GENDER EQUALITY PLANS MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

16.10.2023 3

Structure

MAIN PROBLEMS CONTINUOUS GE ASSESSMENT IN SALTOpower DELIVERABLES

Introduction

16.10.2023 4

16.10.2023

Why?

“Equality between men and women is a principle of citizenship established in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948”

Plano para a Igualdade de Género 2022-2023, UÉvora

“positive impact on the reputation as an employer”

Rahmengleichstellungsplan des Deutschen Zentrums für Luft- und Raumfahrt, 2022-2025

Gender difference as a positive working tool for teams: different approaches, different points of view contribute to research.

Introduction

5

16.10.2023

Your opinion...

Do you think there is gender equality:

- in general?
- in your institutions?
- in SALTOpower?

Introduction

6

Concepts

16.10.2023 7

16.10.2023

49,6% women in world population
38,7% women in the workforce

Concepts

Dra. M^a Dolores Arenas e Dra. Berta Puértolas, Universidad de Extremadura *in* "A mulher no trabalho: desigualdade e barreiras de género", II Jornada Ibérica "O verbo Ser no feminino".

8

16.10.2023

The glass ceiling effect

The glass ceiling (invisible barrier) effect is the pervasive resistance to the efforts of women and minorities to reach the top ranks of management in organizations.

Causes:

- socio-cultural factors
- gender roles and stereotypes
- corporate management culture in companies
- sociocultural preconceptions that make it difficult for men to take orders from women
- etc.

Concepts

9

Cement ceiling effect

Cement ceiling is an expression that refers to the internal barriers unconsciously self-imposed by women themselves at the time of career advancement to higher positions of responsibility.

Causes:

- family responsibilities
- domestic work
- career break due to pregnancy and breastfeeding
- etc.

Concepts

The Matilda effect

The Matilda effect is a bias against acknowledging the achievements of women scientists whose work is attributed to their male colleagues. This phenomenon was first described by suffragist and abolitionist Matilda Joslyn Gage.

Concepts

Matilda

Rosalind Franklin

F. Crick and J. Watson
DNA

Now recognized as an important contributor to the 1953 discovery of DNA structure.

SALTOpower

Dominique Livreiro

Gender Equality Plans

In common

European and national legislation, Horizon Europe guidance on gender equality plans.

Gender Equality Plans

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

In common

- Situation diagnosis (enquiries, HR information);
- Objectives to be achieved (planning) and tools (implementation);
- Monitoring.

Gender Equality Plans

Differences

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;

Flexibility of schedules

Use of non-sexist language, **drafting of a practical guide**

Awareness campaigns

Childcare services or reserved places in childcare centres

Online seminars and informative materials (intranet, flyers...)

Promoting the assumption of family responsibilities by men

Family advisory centre (family care, coming back after parental leave...)

Gender Equality Plans

Differences

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;

Teleworking for workers with specific family situations

Economical support during parental leave

Day care centres for elderly cohabiting parents

Meetings within working hours/ **2 hours long max.**

Summer centres/Holiday activities for children and transport

Online workshops for children

Part-time work during parental leave

Gender Equality Plans

Differences

2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;

Monitoring the composition of the leadership bodies

Training with experts and mentoring

Gender Equality Plans

Differences

3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression:

- Equality in selection boards
- Positive discrimination in hiring
- Female candidates encouraged
- Celebration of Girls national day (visit to installations)
- Visits by girls from regional schools
- Neutral job advertisements
- Sensitising managers to GE and selection procedures (e.g. it is unacceptable to ask about marital status, pregnancy or family responsibilities in interviews)

UÉVORA, DLR, ENEA

Differences

4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content:

- Include this theme in the study programmes
- Training and raising awareness
- Target quotas for scientific staff (30%)
- Accelerated recruitment processes
- Increasing women's visibility, promotional video about female researchers and technicians R&D activities
- Health promotion for women workers, gender-related workplace risk assessment

UÉVORA, DLR, ENEA

Differences

5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

- Training
 - Scientific and artistic events
 - Lack of knowledge of the law
- Complaints - How (e-mail), to whom, how to manage, conduct code, internet materials or intranet guide
- Confidentially appointed persons with specific training to share information
- Confidential counselling helpline
- Seminars and campaigns

UÉVORA, DLR, ENEA

Conclusions

- Predominantly non-sexist cultures, but certain positions or functions occupied by men;
- Women more interested in this theme (UEVORA);
- The need to use inclusive language;
- Questions/doubts about how or to whom to report.

Gender Equality Plans

SALTOpower

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Dominique Livreiro

Main achievements

- Gender equality plans;
- More often discussion of the topic;
- Legislation;
- More women in leadership positions;
- More flexible parental leave policies;
- More inclusive working environments.

Main achievements

DESPACHO N.º 79/2023

Código de conduta para a prevenção e combate ao assédio no trabalho na Universidade de Évora e Serviços de Ação Social

Ao abrigo do disposto na alínea n) do n.º 1 do artigo 23.º dos Estatutos da Universidade de Évora, homologados pelo Despacho Normativo n.º 7/2021, publicado no Diário da República, 2.ª série, n.º 30, de 12 de fevereiro 2021, após consulta pública, é aprovado e posto em vigor o "Código de conduta para a prevenção e combate ao assédio no trabalho na universidade de Évora", que se anexa ao presente despacho e que deste passa a fazer parte integrante.

A Reitora da Universidade de Évora, em 26 de junho de 2023

Main achievements

Code of conduct for the prevention and combat of harassment at work at the University of Évora

25

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Dominique Livreiro/Célia Peralta

Main problems

16.10.2023
26

- How to report?
- Men should be part of the discussion?
- Women are against themselves?
- Less women in STEM?
- Specific examples?

Of the total number of scientists and engineers, only 40% are women.

Hostile and sexist working environments, the assignment of boring tasks, the pay gap and the lack of career development and recognition.

<https://epale.ec.europa.eu/pt/blog/desigualdade-de-genero-na-educacao-stem>

Main problems

27

Main problems

1 - Hierarchical superior or Rector

2 - Internal reporting irregularities channel

Canal de Denúncia Interno

In progress, with the involvement Gender equality and inclusion office, informatic services and Etic Commission

3 - Open Door Vice-Rector initiative: to all members of the University, listening to people and consolidating a culture of dialogue

Are the consequences for offenders fair?

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Dominique Livreiro

Continuous GE assessment in SALTOpower

Continuous GE assessment in SALTOpower

Task 1.4: Gender Equality (Leader: UEVORA; Participants: DLR, ENEA) M1-M36

Led by UEvora-SCC, this task aims at the development and implementation of questionnaires, monitoring procedures and enhancement strategies aiming Gender equality in the access to research and technical-administrative positions in the Consortium institutions. Grounded on the individual experience of the female participants in the project, Gender equality measures will be discussed and presented in 4 dedicated Seminars alongside Project Meetings and hosted, in turns, by Widening and TOP partners. The description and assessment of Gender Equality measures will be presented in a dedicated D1.6.

1. Work-life balance and organisational culture;
 2. Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
 3. Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
 4. Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
 5. Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.
- a. **Enquires**; - anonymous (and a smaller version to apply to FTS participants)
 - b. **HR information** (including FTS);
 - c. **Dedicated seminars**;
 - d. Enhancement strategies;
 - e. Monitoring procedures;
 - f. Positive discrimination of women in hiring;
 - g. Salary review to guarantee equality;

SALTOpower

Deliverables

16.10.2023 ³³

Deliverable No and Name	TYPE	DUE DATE
D1.6 Gender Equality Report	R — Document, report	M34

WP1 Deliverable

- **ProM#3 GE Seminar**

European Facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications
GA Number: 101079303
European Research Executive Agency REA.C3

Funded by the European Union

SALTOpower

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
German Aerospace Center

ENEA
European Nuclear Agency

Gender Equality

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023 1

Structure

SALTOpower

Dominique Livreiro

Webinar

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023 3

Project Meeting, Évora 14.-16.10.2023

GENDER EQUALITY IN THE ENERGY SECTOR WEBINAR

14 NOV 2023
15:00-16:30 CET
ONLINE

GREEN DEAL & GENDER EQUALITY

Webinar

Webinar: Moving towards a green and gender equal energy transition

Gender Equality Index 2023

4

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UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA
GABINETE PARA A IGUALDADE DE GÉNERO E INCLUSÃO

Célia Peralta

Rush hour of life

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023 5

The *rush hour of life**

from 30 to 49 years old - what is the relevance of this stage of life ?

a period of intense pressure **that stems from a set of competing or even contradictory demands:**

- it is the **time of family formation**, but it is also
- the **time for professional affirmation and progression.**

Rush hour of life

But this phase tends to be experienced differently by women and men:
women **spend on average more hours a week** looking after their families.

*Torres, A., et al. (2019). Work, family and living conditions in Portugal and Europe

Consequences: have more pressure, more physical and psychological fatigue, which results in higher consumption of antidepressants

6

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Dominique Livreiro/Célia Peralta

Unconscious bias

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023 7

Unconscious bias

Unconscious biases are learnt assumptions, beliefs or attitudes of which we are not necessarily aware. Everyone has such biases (are formed at 3/4 years of age) and resorts to them as mental shortcuts for faster information processing.

Unconscious bias

- | | |
|-----------------------|-----------|
| Skin colour | Accent |
| Level of education | Weight |
| Age | Sexuality |
| Socio economic status | Gender |

8

Unconscious bias

- Unconscious gender bias remains a significant barrier to women's career advancement. It is also difficult to identify and prevent.
- Unconscious gender bias remains a significant barrier to men's participation in household tasks, caring for children and the elderly

Unconscious gender bias is defined as unintentional and automatic mental associations based on **gender stereotyping** specific genders, stemming from traditions, norms, values, culture and/or experience, that establishes women's and men's have certain **natural different roles in life**

9

Toxic masculinity

Men:

- must **take risks**, violence, **domination**, the primacy of work
- have **to be livelihood and safety** of their families
- don't express your emotions and especially **don't cry**
- don't know how take care of their children, so **they need a wife**

"who look after the children are faggots!"

Consequences: Self-reliance and emotional repression are correlated with increased psychological problems in men such as depression, increased stress, and substance use disorders

10

Unconscious bias in the job market

- Typically female jobs include babysitters, preschool and kindergarten teachers, nurses, and receptionists.

- Typically male jobs include truck drivers, electricians, and firefighters.

Fixed and reproduces different roles because of biological sex and the social construction of gender

11

Inspeção-Geral da Saúde abre inspeção no caso das gémeas luso-brasileiras

ULTIMAS | VIDEOS | QUERER Localiza | QUERER local / Home | SAALICOP Apoio às vendas | DECEA | DAN-PC

Portuguesas ganham menos 13% do que os portugueses, diz estudo da CGTP

Agência Lusa, AG
1 mai, 09:54

Diferença é maior entre os que ganham mais dinheiro

PORTDATA
ESTATÍSTICAS ECONÓMICAS PORTUGUESAS E EUROPEIAS

ESTATÍSTICAS PUBLICAÇÕES QUADROS RESUMO SIMULADORES CENSOS 2021 CINCO DÉCADAS DE DEMOCRACIA

Portada > Portugal > Emprego e Mercado de Trabalho > Salários

Disparidade entre sexos no ganho médio mensal dos trabalhadores por conta de outrem: total e por nível de qualificação

Qual é a diferença no salário médio, por mês, com férias, extras, subsídios ou prémios, entre mulheres e homens em percentagem do salário médio mensal dos homens?

Indicador
Total níveis de qualificação

2021	-16,0 %
1985	-27,1 %

Campeão azul para ver o gráfico completo

EXCLUSIVO NATALIDADE

Desigualdade salarial entre homens e mulheres ajuda a afundar a natalidade em Portugal

O facto de as mulheres ganharem menos do que os homens é um dos entraves à natalidade, diz estudo. A precariedade dos jovens também ajuda a explicar porque têm os portugueses cada vez menos filhos.

Natália Faria
2 de Junho de 2023, 15:00

Assine já

“The increased presence of women in the labour market has not resulted in a decrease in fertility, but the wage gap between women and men has. Women invest more time in their professional qualifications. However, they still earn less and are less represented in top positions. And this pay gap results in fewer financial resources for women to plan their parenting decisions (...).”

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UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA
Dominique Livreiro

Continuous GE assessment in SALTOpower

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023

- a. **Enquires** - anonymous (and a smaller version to apply to FTS participants);
- b. **HR information** (including FTS);
- c. **Dedicated seminars**;

- Work-life balance and organisational culture;
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making;
- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression;
- Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content;
- Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

Continuous GE assessment in SALTOpower

SALTOpower

UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA

Deliverables

Évora, 14.-16.11.2023 16

Deliverable No and Name	TYPE	DUE DATE
D1.6 Gender Equality Report	R — Document, report	M34

WP1 Deliverable

Task 1.4 completion

Task	Done	To do
T1.4 Gender Equality	Seminar	Seminars Enquires HR information D1.6

- **ProM#4 GE Seminar**

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UNIVERSIDADE DE ÉVORA
Dominique Livreiro

Gender equality aspects

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

GE INQUIRY

GENDER INSENSITIVE LANGUAGE

SALTOpower

Dominique Livreiro

Inquiry

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

SALTOpower

Dominique Livreiro

Gender-sensitive language

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

Why use gender-sensitive language

In order to tackle gender inequality, we must look at the way we communicate. Using gender-sensitive language can:

- Make it easier to see important differences between the needs of women and men;
- Challenge unconscious assumptions people have about gender roles in society;
- Lay the foundation for greater gender equality throughout society;
- Raise awareness of how language affects our behaviour;
- Make people more comfortable with expressing themselves and behaving in ways that were once not considered 'typical' of their gender.

Gender Equality

Gender insensitive language

Gender Equality

Preamble

0/9 found

Precarious employment is arguably man's greatest challenge in the modern age. Michland is still recovering from the effects of the recent economic crisis, but the benefits have not been equally shared amongst her citizens. Although unemployment has begun to fall, the rise of low-pay, insecure jobs is threatening the ability of families to make ends meet. More and more families are facing poverty and insecurity, through no fault of their own. This development is wreaking havoc on workers from all occupations—from builders and pollicemen through to teachers and even waitresses.

On 1 November 2000, a spokesman for the President stated:

"The failures of the last government have left many families struggling. Our social inclusion strategy embodies the virile action needed to overcome the spectre of precarious employment and give everyone a decent chance in life"

Gender insensitive language

Gender Equality

Objectives

This strategy aims to ensure that:

- Every employee has sufficient income and social protection to protect himself from poverty;
- There are adequate measures to support the work-life balance of women;
- Early years interventions are in place for parents and children at risk of poverty;
- Boys and girls everywhere have access to a decent education, regardless of their income

Gender Equality

Preamble

Precarious employment is arguably man's greatest challenge in the modern age. Michland is still recovering from the effects of the recent economic crisis, but the benefits have not been equally shared amongst her citizens. Although unemployment has begun to fall, the rise of low-pay, insecure jobs is threatening the ability of families to make ends meet. More and more families are facing poverty and insecurity, through no fault of their own. This development is wreaking havoc on workers from all occupations—from builders and pollicemen through to teachers and even waitresses.

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COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

Gender Equality

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On 1 November 2000, a **spokesperson** for the President stated:

*"The failures of the last government have left many families struggling. Our social inclusion strategy embodies the **strong** action needed to overcome the spectre of precarious employment and give everyone a decent chance in life"*

Objectives

This strategy aims to ensure that:

- All employees has sufficient income and social protection to protect **themselves** from poverty;
- There are adequate measures to support the reconciliation of family and professional responsibilities of **parents with young children, and particularly to support new mothers, who continue to bear the majority of caring responsibilities**
- Early years interventions are in place for parents and children at risk of poverty;
- **Girls and boys** everywhere have access to a decent education, regardless of their income

COLOGNE, 02.-05.07.2024

Task 1.4 completion

Task	Done	To do
T1.4 Gender Equality	Seminars GEP comparison Inquiry	Inquiry analysis HR information analysis List of problems and solutions D1.6

APPENDIX 3: SALTOPOWER TEAM GE SURVEY

Perguntas Respostas 19 Definições

Gender Equality assessment in SALTOpower

B *I* U ↻ ✕

This inquiry is **anonymous** and the data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the SALTOpower project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored in a folder restricted to SALTOpower partners (UEVORA, DLR and ENEA) until the end of the project (2025).

Please, answer the following questions by selecting only one of the available answers and only elaborate on your answers when lines are provided. In questions with options 1 to 5: 1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree".

This questionnaire takes about 5 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance.

1. Sector

19 respostas

2. Gender

19 respostas

3. Age

19 respostas

4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?

19 respostas

4.1. If yes, have you read it?

17 respostas

5. In your opinion, is there gender equality... 5.1. in society in general? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

19 respostas

5.2. in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 m... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

19 respostas

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?

19 respostas

6.1. If yes, was it ...

8 respostas

7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organization? (1 means "...rtially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

19 respostas

7.1. In upper management positions, are there gender inequalities? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
 19 respostas

8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
 19 respostas

8.1. Do you know any work-life balance measures available in your organization? Which one?
 19 respostas

8.1.1. If yes, kindly specify:

8 respostas

Parental leaf, Home Office, Part time
Parental Leave, Homeoffice...
Continuous journey
Homeoffice flexibility
Floating hour system, parental leave
Horários flexíveis, jornada continua
Flexible work schedules
Homeoffice

9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially"...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

19 respostas

10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents? (1 mean...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

19 respostas

11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?

19 respostas

11.1. If yes, ...

1 resposta

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?

19 respostas

12.1. If yes, ...

7 respostas

12.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

3 respostas

Women no placed on positions due to the intent of having children in coming near future

Not selected for an internship because the working environment is mostly men and the company does not feel comfortable selecting a female despite being the top candidate on qualifications level.

Sometimes, women are not seen as só good professional as men

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?

19 respostas

13.1.If yes, ...

6 respostas

13.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

2 respostas

Professors harassment of student

From teachers to students.

14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organization?

19 respostas

15. In your opinion, is it important to address gender equality issues in research projects such as SALTOpower?

19 respostas

16. In your opinion, is there gender equality in the SALTOpower project?

19 respostas

17. Do you have suggestions on how to improve gender equality in the SALTOpower project (e.g. providing part-time job vacancies, providing personal protective equipment in sizes suitable for women and men)?

1 resposta

It is a problema of society in general, but talking about this questions on different contexts is always important to help to get improvements

APPENDIX 4: FTSs GE SURVEY

Perguntas Respostas 25 Definições

Gender Equality assessment in SALTOPower

B *I* U ↻ ✖

This enquiry is **anonymous** and the data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the SALTOPower project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be stored in a folder restricted to SALTOPower partners (UEVORA, DLR and ENEA) until the end of the project (2025).

Please, answer the following questions by selecting only one of the available answers and only elaborate on your answers when lines are provided. In questions with options 1 to 5: 1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means "I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree".

This questionnaire takes about 5 minutes to complete. Thank you in advance.

1. Sector

25 respostas

2. Gender
25 respostas

3. Age
25 respostas

4. Does the institution where you work/study have a Gender Equality Plan?
25 respostas

4.1. If yes, have you read it?

22 respostas

5. In your opinion, is there gender equality... 5.1. in society in general? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "...I partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

25 respostas

5.2. in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "I don't agree or disagree", 4 means... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

25 respostas

6. Have you ever felt discriminated because of your gender?

25 respostas

6.1. If yes, was it ...

9 respostas

7. Do you think that there are equal opportunities (e.g. employment, promotions) for men and women at your work/study organization? (1 mean...artially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

25 respostas

7.1. In upper management positions, are there gender inequalities? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
25 respostas

8. Is work-life balance favoured in your work/study organization? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially", 3 means "... partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")
25 respostas

8.1. Do you know any work-life balance measures available in your organization? Which one?
25 respostas

8.1.1. If yes, kindly specify:

9 respostas

Hybrid working 1 day a week when taking care of children

Parents

Working from home

Home Office

Emergency child care, seminars, sports, limiting extra hours, kindergarten places, flexible work days, hours and places

Horario flexivel, jornada continua

part time, parental leave

Days off at Christmas and Easter in addition to the usual holidays

Possibility of continuous journey

9. Are women and men assigned different tasks in the same job category? (1 means "I completely disagree", 2 means "I disagree partially"...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

25 respostas

10. Do you feel that you are discriminated at work because you are responsible for looking after children, the elderly or other dependents? (1 mean...partially agree" and 5 means "I completely agree")

25 respostas

11. Do you often hear or say sexist comments?

25 respostas

11.1. If yes, ...

7 respostas

12. Have you experienced, know about or perceived any gender discrimination?

25 respostas

12.1. If yes, ...

8 respostas

- In the current place of work/study
- In a previous place of work/study
- outside the place of work/study

12.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

4 respostas

Position won by women but at the end they were not included because they were envisaging to have children in the near future

Various but not so critical

Women were automatically assigned subordinate tasks like doing a protocol.

Not being heard when I made a comment and when someone said the same thing, it was heard and considered

13. Have you experienced, know about or perceived sexual harassment?

25 respostas

- Yes
- No
- Don't know/ won't answer

13.1. If yes, ...

8 respostas

- In the current place of work/study
- In a previous place of work/study
- outside the place of work/study

13.1.1. Could you summarise the situation (without identifying names)?

4 respostas

- Sexual harassment of interns by workshop employees
- People assume I need/search a partner just because I am a young looking woman without knowing anything about me
- Sexist comments and looks
- Professors harassing students

14. Do you know what to do or who to contact if you experience, perceive or know of sexual harassment or gender discrimination in the work/study organization?

25 respostas

- Yes
- No
- Don't know/ won't answer

Do you have suggestions?

2 respostas

- some answers are rather yes and no, but explanation is agree and disagree - I didn't know how to answer-prepare more carefully such form!
- Speak open and loud about this topic